

ISic0267

I.Sicily inscription 0267

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Messiae · Prisci · fil(iae) · Crispinae
2. flaminicae · divae · Aug(ustae)
3. ex · testamento · Messi · Modiani · patris
4. Modianus · frater

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001 and CIL

Translation (en)

To Messia Crispina, daughter of Priscus, flaminica of Diva Augusta. Her brother Modianus set it up by the will of his father Messius Modianus.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284762

EDR 033602

EDCS 21900297

PHI 313696

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.6978 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At xiv

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0267. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334805>